

THE ROLE OF MATERIAL AND WRITTEN SOURCES IN THE STUDY OF HISTORY

Turobova Nilufar Umidullayevna

Director of general education school No. 4 in Boysun district

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10552792>

Abstract. *This article discusses the role of material and written sources in studying the history of Uzbekistan.*

Keywords: *history of Uzbekistan, material sources, written sources, evidential sources, normative sources, reasoning, thinking, secondary education, linguistic data, artistic resources, efficiency.*

The scientist who theoretically described the concept of historical source is L. Danilevskiy. According to the theory of knowledge, the "source" can be any information that can be perceived by our senses with empirical information. In the scientific-empirical sense, any existing object from which knowledge about another object can be obtained not for itself, but through its close means can be called a source. This concept proposed in the field of history includes the concept of the existence of an object and its suitability for studying another object. In fact, for any researcher engaged in the science of history, such an object is imagined as "information" in his mind. The researcher not only does not recognize it as his own concept, but sees its content in practice. Otherwise, the source may not be the object of emotional reception of the researcher. Based on the sources, it will not be possible for this object to know the reality. Because any historical research sets the goal of knowing reality according to a certain source.

The difference between a historical source and historical evidence is that if the concept of historical evidence includes the concept of the impact of individuality on the material environment, then any historical source can be called historical evidence. But the historian uses such evidence as a source to learn about other evidence. A source for the science of history is any existing object that provides information about another object, not for its own sake. . A historical source is the result of human creativity in a broad sense. In many cases, the author of the source is unknown. If a resource is created by a group of people, this creation is called "public" (for example, language, folk songs and epics). Historical sources can be systematized differently according to research goals. The most general of them is to determine the importance of historical sources for historical knowledge. In this sense, sources are studied according to their value level or certain historical evidence. On this basis, it is easy to differentiate according to the level of resources that describe their valuable content.

The role and importance of sources in the study of the history of Uzbekistan and the history of Uzbekistan. That is why they are considered the spiritual and cultural heritage of the nation and the people, invaluable cultural and historical wealth, and are carefully and carefully preserved in special archives (archives), libraries and museums, as well as family archives. It is passed down from language to language through folklore coming to us on the basis of the narrative of historical events and events, normative materials.

Therefore, it is necessary to shed light on history only through historical sources and monuments - by obtaining historical data and evidence, their comparative comparison and historical generalization, analysis of the causes and consequences of historical and cultural

processes and events, their essence, analyses on the basis of which the possibilities of giving scientifically based conclusions will be expanded. Historical sources have ancient and current (daily) significance from the point of view of the period. They also have the status of primary and secondary importance according to their content and essence. A primary source includes the original copy of historical documents. Secondary sources are published copies of primary sources, articles and books. Historical sources include all things that have remained since ancient times, that is, all material culture objects and objects created by human hands and intelligence, structures, written monuments, customs, traditions, languages, etc. Sources of studying the history of Uzbekistan in modern literature are conditionally divided into the following six groups:

1. Written sources - epigraphic monuments, i.e., stone, metal, bone and ceramic inscriptions, "Avesta", cuneiform inscriptions, messages of ancient and medieval authors, graffiti, i.e., hand-made buildings, metal objects, traces left on vessels, papyrus, parchment and papers manuscripts, printed materials.

2. Material or archaeological resources - labor and combat weapons, handicrafts, dishes, household items, clothes, livestock equipment, coins, art objects, architectural structures, houses studied as a result of archaeological research - site remains, defense structures, material sources are of great importance for the recovery of our history from unwritten times.

3. Ethnographic data - people's way of life and lifestyle, customs and traditions, holidays and religious beliefs, economic activities, etc. from the earliest times to the late Middle Ages, provides valuable information about traditions specific to ethnic groups.

4. Linguistic information - includes information about the reflection of ancient languages in written, artistic and oral speech, historical roots of similarities in the languages and dialects of different peoples.

This information is of great importance in the study of the ethnic origin and occupations of peoples and peoples, migration processes, religious beliefs, culture, and lifestyle.

5. Photographic documents are relatively new, they are a confirmation of the opinions expressed about events and certain persons.

6. Archive materials - the information stored in the central and current archives is very important in the study of socio-economic, cultural and political processes from the middle of the 19th century to today.

The study of historical sources itself, that is, source studies, is a special field of history, which is of great importance in the development of history and the writing of history.

Currently, the science of source studies is developing widely. It relies on the above-mentioned methodological scientific-theoretical, ideological-ideological basis and scientific methods.

The science of source studies is mainly concerned with the study of historical sources, while determining the value of sources, authentic and non-authentic, and classifying them into categories. For example, material and spiritual monuments and physical - ethnographic, linguistic and oral (folklore) resources among them.

Identification and classification of sources, their scientific value is divided into areas such as definition, analysis, history of creation, study of conditions.

The conclusion is that the sources are a real reflection of the historical process and realities, and should be a reflection of historicity. That's why their historical significance and historicity are high, and they closely help the historical truth to emerge. It is known that history is created by the

people. The importance of ancillary subjects in the teaching and learning of this history, created over thousands of years, is immeasurable. For example, archeology, ethnography, anthropology, numismatics, linguistics, historiography, terminology, sociology, historical demography, historical geography, geopolitics, philosophy, local studies, cartography, economics, fields such as cultural studies and religious studies are among auxiliary sciences.

However, in the creation of the history of Uzbekistan, the data of a number of auxiliary sciences remain out of the attention of scientists. For example, most of the existing study guides and textbooks do not provide the historiography of the topic covered. Short, excursus in the textbooks being created for specialist students

If the historiography of a certain period, topic and problem is covered in this way, it will not be without benefits for our talented young people who can conduct research in the future. Also, knowledge of historiography is very important for young scientists to choose promising and current topics.

Historical sources have theoretical and practical value. In theory, they are important and necessary to know the historical reality, and in practice to act in it, to participate in the cultural life of mankind. Historical sources are important in the discussion of evidence that has not existed for a long time. For example, on the basis of historical sources, it is possible to talk about the great Timur or about the more ancient Khorezm, Sogdian and Bactrian writings. Without historical sources, the past history of mankind cannot be reconstructed. Because the past development of humanity does not exist in its entirety today. It is known by some traces and remains that have reached the present day. Traces and remains of the past can be directly studied in historical sources. Historical evidence lies within the historical source. Human history cannot be reconstructed without evidence from the source. It must be confirmed in order to receive the status of evidence. Due to the fact that the historical source is stable in form, it can be studied for a long time. The researcher can return to it several times. The source contains a rich and varied treasure of human thought. The study of this treasure makes it possible to restore the main signs (values) of our history and culture and to ensure succession for the future development of our culture.

REFERENCES

1. Sagdullayev A.S. O‘zbekiston tarixi. Toshkent, 1998-yil.
2. Алимов И.А. Архившунослик. Ўқув қўлланма – Андижон: АДУ, 2005.
3. Аҳмедов Б. Ўзбекистон тарихи манбалари. (қадимги замон ва Ўрта асрлар). – Т., 2001.
4. Ахмедов Б.А. Историко-географическая литература Средней Азии XV-XVIII вв. – Т.: Фан, 1985.
5. Buriyeva X.A., Nazarov A.Y., Abbasov B.B. Arxiv ishi nazariyasi va amaliyoti. –Т.: Turoniqbol. 2019.
6. Саидбобоев З. Европада Ўрта Осиёга оид тарихий-картографик маълумотлар (XVI-XIX асрлар). – Т.: Фан, 2008.
7. Ўзбекистоннинг ислом цивилизациясига қўшган ҳиссаси // Халқаро конференция материаллари. – Тошкент-Самарқанд: Имом Бухорий республика илмий-маърифий маркази нашриёти, 2007.
8. Umarali Kadirov. FACTORS AND IMPORTANCE OF FORMING PERSONAL CONSCIOUSNESS IN THE INFORMATION SOCIETY. American Journal of Pedagogical and Educational Research. Volume 18, | November, 2023.